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Design and Fabrication of a Novel On-Chip Pressure Sensor for Microchannels.[†]

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Pressure is important in virtually all problems in fluid dynamics from macro-scale to micro/nano-scale flows. Although technologies are well developed for its measurement at the macroscopic scale, pressure quantification at the microscopic scale is still not trivial. This study reports the design and fabrication of an on-chip sensor that enables quantification of pressure in microfluidic devices based on a novel technique called astigmatic particle tracking. With this technique, thin membranes that sense pressure variations in the fluid flow can be characterized conveniently by imaging the shapes of the particles embedded in the membranes. This innovative design only relies on the reflected light from the back of the microchannel, rendering the sensor to be separate and noninvasive to the flow of interest. This sensor was then applied to characterize the pressure drop in single-phase flows with an accuracy of ~ 70 Pa and good agreement was obtained between the sensor, a commercial pressure transducer and numerical simulation results. Additionally, the sensor successfully measured the capillary pressure across an air-water interface with a 7% deviation from the theoretical value. To the best of our knowledge, this pore-scale capillary pressure quantification is achieved for the first time using an on-chip pressure sensor of this kind. This study provides a novel method for in-situ quantification of local pressure and thus opens the door to a renewed understanding of pore-scale physics of local pressure in multi-phase flow in porous media.

1 Introduction

Pressure measurement is of crucial importance in fluid mechanics to describe and understand various flows. In particular, precise measurement and control of pressure with high spatial and temporal resolutions in microfluidic systems are key to numerous scientific and engineering applications, ranging from sample manipulation in biological studies^{1–4} to the evaluation of capillary pressure in multi-phase flow in porous media, which is relevant to applications like tissue engineering, biological flows, CO₂ sequestration and even enhanced oil recovery (EOR).^{5–7} For instance, capillary pressure is central to the description of multi-phase flow in porous media^{8–15}. Conventional mathematical models of multi-phase flow in porous media have been inevitably relying on empirical relations of capillary pressure which are well known to be hysteretic^{8,9}. It is increasingly accepted that direct *in-situ* measurement of capillary pressure at the microscopic scale will be extremely valuable to mitigate such hysteresis and thus achieve a unique description of the state of the porous medium flow sys-

tem.^{16–18} As another example, in evaporative cooling^{19–21} and flow boiling heat transfer²², local vapor pressure in a bubble plays an important role in bubble growth and departure dynamics, which defines the overall heat transfer performance, thus rendering pressure characterization at the microscopic level a critical need to achieve a fundamental understanding of flow evaporating and boiling processes.

Currently, a number of miniature pressure sensors are commercially available with the advancement of technologies including piezoresistive, capacitive, optical, interferometric and optofluidic pressure sensors.^{23,24} However, direct integration of such sensors into microfluidic devices can be challenging because of their still relatively large sizes compared with typical microchannels. Additionally, multi-step fabrication processes are often required to enable such integration.¹⁸ Therefore, direct on-chip pressure sensors become highly promising and desirable.

In the past two decades, several on-chip pressure measurement methods have been developed employing various working principles. Abkarian et al.²⁵ were among the first ones to contribute to this advances, and they designed a differential manometer based on the interface movements between two immiscible fluids in a microchannel. Alternatively, Shen et al.²⁶, Srivastava and Burns²⁷, and Hoera et al.²⁸ took advantage of the compressibility of air to measure pressure in the target channel by monitoring the volumetric response of an air bubble that was intentionally

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44 trapped in a side cavity. Probably the most popular design is the
 45 membrane-based approach. The basic idea of this design is to
 46 create a thin membrane adjacent to the target microchannel as
 47 the sensing element that deflects subject to pressure variation in
 48 the target microchannel. The membrane deflection can be read
 49 out optically or electrically, which is then correlated to the actual
 50 pressure change through a calibration step. Silicon²⁹ and poly-
 51 dimethylsiloxane (PDMS)^{17,23,30,31} are among the most common
 52 materials for building such membranes for their low cost and ease
 53 of fabrication.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagrams illustrating the basic elements in a typical membrane-based pressure sensor: (a) a design with a closed sensing chamber directly below the target channel, and (b) a design with an open sensing chamber placed remotely to the side of the target channel.

54 A typical membrane-based pressure sensor consists of three lay-
 55 ers as illustrated in Figure 1a: (i) a bottom layer embedded with
 56 pressure taps called sensing chambers of hundreds of microme-
 57 ters thick; (ii) a sensing PDMS membrane with a thickness rang-
 58 ing from a few to several tens of micrometers; (iii) and a top layer
 59 containing the target channel whose thickness can range from a
 60 few micrometers to a few millimeters depending on its intended
 61 function. The three layers are often fabricated separately and
 62 then assembled employing plasma assisted bonding. While cer-
 63 tain designs put the sensing chambers directly above or below the
 64 target flow channel³⁰ (c.f. Figure 1a), others connect the sensing
 65 chambers and the target channel *via* auxiliary transferring chan-
 66 nels to make room for signal readout as illustrated in Figure 1b.³¹
 67 The sensing chambers can be either closed or open to the atmo-
 68 sphere through a venting channel, with the latter resulting in a
 69 constant pressure within the sensing chambers, which has been
 70 shown to increase the measurement sensitivity (c.f. Figure 1b).³⁰

71 With the three-layer design, pressure measurement is conven-
 72 iently transformed into quantification of membrane deflection,
 73 which has been achieved *via* approaches mainly falling into two
 74 categories: the optical schemes and the electrical schemes. The
 75 optical schemes often use a microscope and a camera to correlate
 76 the membrane deflection with a certain optical output, such as
 77 image intensity³², contrast²³ or interference patterns³⁰. Orth et
 78 al.¹⁷ characterized membrane deflection based on the goodness
 79 of focus of a reference target. When coupled with transmitted
 80 light, the membrane effectively works as a lens, which changes
 81 the optical path as deflection is increased under increasing pres-
 82 sure, causing the focal plane and image focus to shift accordingly.
 83 The similar idea was adopted by Chaudhury et al. in a later
 84 study²³, where membrane deflection was instead inferred based
 85 on image contrast. Song and Psaltis³⁰ leveraged interferometry,
 86 where the membrane, upon illumination by monochromatic light,
 87 generates interference patterns that depend on pressure. Chung
 88 et al.³¹ leveraged a suspension of fluorescent particles and cre-

89 atively measured membrane deflection through the amount of
 90 depleted fluorescent particles in the sensing chamber. In general,
 91 optical schemes are accurate and easy to set up, as the required
 92 equipment (e.g., cameras and microscopes) is in many cases al-
 93 ready available in those experiments (e.g., for flow or cell visu-
 94 alization). On the other hand, the electrical schemes detect the
 95 change of electrical resistance³³⁻³⁶ or capacitance^{37,38} to infer
 96 the membrane deflection. While the electrical schemes need no
 97 more than a simple circuit and a multimeter to perform the mea-
 98 surement, the fabrication of the devices can be much more com-
 99 plicated due to the requirements of on-chip electrodes and other
 100 electrical elements. It is worth noting that recently the use of
 101 liquid metals has made such fabrication significantly easier for in-
 102 dividual pressure sensors as illustrated by Zhou et al.³⁹ and other
 103 researchers^{33,36}. However, when multiplexed microscale sensors
 104 (i.e., an array or matrix of *independent* sensors) are needed, the
 105 electrode matrix, lead wires and sensing channels can still be
 106 challenging to fabricate on polymer membranes such as PDMS.

107 Although these previous designs have greatly improved our
 108 ability to characterize pressure in various microfluidic devices, we
 109 note that none of them seems to be suited to our specific appli-
 110 cation. That is to map capillary pressure distribution in multi-
 111 phase flow in porous media^{11,15}. For instance, many previous
 112 designs used auxiliary/transferring channels to facilitate signal
 113 readout, which however adds significant dead volume to the sys-
 114 tem and thus reduces the responsiveness of the sensors.³¹ Ad-
 115 ditionally, many designs used transmitted light for signal read-
 116 out^{17,23}, where illumination light runs through all three layers:
 117 the membrane, the sensing chamber and the target channel. In
 118 that case, the output signal can be significantly affected by the
 119 flow pattern within the target channel, rendering them not suit-
 120 able for measurement of multi-phase flows. Moreover, while
 121 several studies demonstrated multiplex pressure measurement,
 122 a majority of previous designs only perform single-point mea-
 123 surements as opposed to pressure field mapping. To overcome
 124 these challenges, this work proposes a novel design of microflu-
 125 idic pressure sensor to achieve fast and precise pressure measure-
 126 ment in microchannels. In this current design, the membrane de-
 127 flection will be detected through particle astigmatism inspired by
 128 the astigmatic particle tracking velocimetry (APT_V)^{40,41}, which
 129 offers the benefits of simpler fabrication, easier implementation
 130 and better versatility. The innovation of current work is two-fold:
 131 (i) we have successfully demonstrated the effectiveness of APT_V
 132 in the quantification of membrane deflection and pressure mea-
 133 surement; (ii) we have, to the best of our knowledge, for the first
 134 time applied such pressure sensors to capillary pressure quantifi-
 135 cation in multiphase flow. This work thus paves the way for 2D
 136 pressure field mapping in porous medium flows.

2 Experimental Description

2.1 Pressure Sensor Design

139 Our membrane-based pressure sensor also consists of three lay-
 140 ers, as shown in Figure 2a. Compared with previous designs, the
 141 novel aspect of this design is that 1 μ m fluorescent particles are
 142 embedded into the sensing membrane to facilitate characteriza-

Fig. 2 (a) A schematic diagram illustrating the three-layer design of our pressure sensor: the top layer contains the flow channel made of PDMS; the middle layer is PDMS membrane with fluorescent particles embedded within; and the bottom layer contains the sensing chamber fabricated in optical glue (NOA81). Note that a glass slide is used to serve as a rigid substrate to minimize deformation of the device. (b, c) the state of the membrane and the corresponding particle images when the device is subject to *low* pressures. (d, e) the state of the membrane and the corresponding particle images when the device is subject to *high* pressures.

143 tion of membrane deflection using the astigmatic particle tracking
 144 technique (see details below in § 2.2). Briefly, when the applied

Fig. 3 A schematic illustrating the working principle of astigmatism.⁴⁰

145 pressure is low, the membrane sits close to its initial position, 146
 147 which is far from the microscope objective (note the objective 148
 149 views from the bottom), causing the embedded particles to form 150
 151 vertical elliptical images on the camera (Figure 2b, c). As the 152
 153 applied pressure increases, the membrane deflects and carries the 154
 155 embedded particles towards the microscope objective to form 156
 157 horizontal elliptical images (Figure 2d, e). Essentially, the mem- 158
 159 brane deflection and thus the applied pressure are measured through 160
 161 the shapes of particle images. The sensing chambers placed right 162
 163 below the target channel are all connected to the atmosphere al- 164
 165 lowing them to stay at atmospheric pressure throughout the exper- 166
 167 iment.¹⁷ This design offers several benefits. It allows for pres- 168
 169 sure measurement at virtually any location of the target channel 170
 171 by conveniently positioning the sensing chamber without any mod- 172
 172 ification of the setup for signal readout. By leveraging APTV, image
 acquisition can be performed using any standard epi-fluorescence
 microscope with minimal modification. Additionally, the sensor
 sensitivity and measurement range can be finely tuned by varying
 the sensing chamber size or membrane thickness. It is also worth
 noting that, although this study focuses on the measurement of
 positive pressures in the target channel, this design is indeed cap-
 able of measuring negative gauge pressures without needing any
 modification. Under negative pressures, the membrane would
 deflect upward, causing the elliptical particle images (c.f. Figure 2c)
 to be even slenderer, from which and the calibration images, the
 corresponding negative pressure can be quantified.

173 2.2 Astigmatic Particle Tracking

174 As mentioned previously, one of the innovative aspects of the de-
175 sign is the use of the APTV technique for membrane deflection
176 quantification.⁴⁰ To achieve that, (i) fluorescent tracer particles
177 are embedded in the membrane during fabrication, and (ii) a
178 cylindrical lens was placed between the microscope objective and
179 the camera as a modification to standard microscopy. As shown
180 in Figure 3, the cylindrical lens, which focuses light within a sin-
181 gle axis only, causes the imaging plane to shift in the x - z plane,
182 without affecting the y - z plane. Particles at different z locations,
183 will be focused differently in both x and y directions, forming dif-
184 ferent shapes of images depending on their z locations. Assuming
185 that there is no relative movement between the particles and the
186 membrane, particle position effectively yields information about
187 membrane deflection. In this current configuration, a particle that
188 is far away from the objective (*i.e.*, higher z location), form verti-
189 cally elongated images (particle B in Figure 3), whereas a particle
190 that is close to the objective tends to form horizontally elongated
191 images (particle A in Figure 3).

192 2.3 Fabrication

193 The device was fabricated in separate layers, which were then as-
194 sembled by bonding all layers together as shown in Figure 4. The
195 microchannel (Layer I) was fabricated employing standard soft
196 lithography⁴², which consists of three major steps: photomask
197 design, SU-8 master fabrication and PDMS molding (Figure 4,
198 Layer I). The photomask was designed in Adobe Illustrator[®],
199 and printed by a third-party company (CAD/Art Services, Inc.).
200 To create the master, a layer of SU-8 3050 (Kayaku Advanced
201 Materials SU-8 3050) was coated on a 4" silicon wafer by spin-
202 ning it at 1000 rpm for 30s, following which a series of pro-
203 cesses including soft baking, exposing, post exposure baking,
204 developing, cleaning, and hard baking were performed sequen-
205 tially, to achieve the designed pattern with a final nominal film
206 thickness of 100 μm . The SU-8 master was then silanized using
207 Trichlorosilane (Sigma-Aldrich 1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluorooctyl) for
208 30 min. Meanwhile, the PDMS polymers were prepared at a ra-
209 tio of 10:1 (pre-polymer:scuring agent), mixed, and degassed for
210 30 min to remove all air bubbles entrained in the polymer during
211 mixing. Finally, the polymer was poured on top the SU-8 master,
212 and baked at 65 °C for 2 hours to cure, following which the PDMS
213 slab was peeled off the SU-8 master, cut into individual devices,
214 and 2 mm holes were punched to serve as fluid delivery ports.

215 The membrane fabrication was conducted employing the spin-
216 coating technique as shown in Figure 4 (Layer II). The goal here
217 is to create a flexible PDMS membrane of approximately 5 μm in
218 thickness with 1 μm fluorescent particle embedded within. To this
219 end, the PDMS mixture prepared again at the 10:1 ratio was di-
220 luted by tert-butyl alcohol (TBA, $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{COH}$) at a ratio of 1:3 by
221 weight (*i.e.*, 1 part of PDMS and 3 parts of TBA). TBA is a tertiary
222 alcohol and can be used to reduce the viscosity of the PDMS mix-
223 ture without causing swelling to the final cured product, which is
224 critical to create thin PDMS films as needed here.⁴³ Then 20 μl
225 suspension of carboxylate-modified fluorescent particles of 1 μm
226 in diameter (FluroSpheres, F8819) was added into 8 ml diluted

PDMS polymer and mixed with the aid of ultrasound. The final
mixture was then poured onto a silanized bare silicon wafer and
spun at 2000 rpm for 5 min. The PDMS film was then baked for 8
minutes at 65 °C to semi-cure. The microchannel (Layer I) fabri-
cated in the previous step was then bonded to the membrane by
slowly and steadily placing it onto the membrane. In this regard,
the semi-cure process of the membrane is critical as it ensures
the PDMS membrane to solidify but still sticky enough to create
good bonding between the two layers. The assembly of the mem-
brane and microchannels was fully cured in the oven for another
2 hours at 65 °C.

For the sensing chambers (Layer III), a PDMS mold containing
the sensing chamber design was first fabricated with the same
procedures used in Layer I, following which optical glue mold-
ing was conducted. The PDMS mold was placed on a flat surface
with the patterned side facing up. Two drops of optical glue (Nor-
land Optical Adhesive 81) were dispensed onto the PDMS sur-
face. Then a clean microscope slide (Fisher Scientific 75 \times 25 mm
144/GR) was placed on top of the optical glue and gently pressed
down to ensure the glue evenly spreads between the PDMS mold
and the microscope slide. The whole assembly was then exposed
under UV light (Thorlabs M385LP1) for 10 minutes. Once the
glue was cured, the PDMS mold was peeled off to expose the
sensing chambers made of optical glue. It is worth noting that,
the sensing chambers could have been fabricated in PDMS too as
in many previous studies^{17,23,31}. In fact, PDMS sensing cham-
bers were initially used in our device, and acceptable results were
achieved. However, we note that the optical glue used herein of-
fers much better optical properties compared with PDMS, which
helped to significantly improve the final particle image quality
and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). In addition, sensing chambers
made of optical glue can be easily peeled off the PDMS part, al-
lowing for them to be reused in multiple devices. Finally, the top
two layers (Layers I and II) were aligned and bonded with the
third layer on an aligning stage (three way translation + rota-
tion), and the nanoports were attached to the inlet and outlet of
the microchannel to facilitate fluid delivery, which completes the
device fabrication.

245 2.4 Device Calibration

246 In order to use the device for accurate pressure measurement,
247 a relationship between the target pressure and membrane de-
248 flection needs to be pre-defined through a calibration step.^{17,31}
249 Herein the calibration procedure simply involves acquiring two
250 sets of images of the membrane: (i) one set of images at a series
251 of prescribed z positions, hereinafter referred to as the position
252 calibration; and (ii) a second set of images of the membrane at a
253 series of prescribed pressures, hereinafter referred to as the pres-
254 sure calibration. The position calibration essentially creates a li-
255 brary of images containing information of particle image shapes
256 at various distances from the microscope objective (Figure 5 [Left
257 Column]). These images were used later as reference images (ef-
258 fectively a ruler) to determine the distance between the mem-
259 brane and the microscope objective for real experimental images.
260 In the position calibration, the objective was initially positioned

Fig. 4 Schematic illustrating the major steps to fabricate the device in layers.

281 at $z = 0 \mu\text{m}$, and gradually moved up towards the device at an
 282 increment of $1 \mu\text{m}$, which was precisely controlled by the focusing
 283 knob on the microscope. On the other hand, the pressure cali-
 284 bration creates a library of images at various prescribed pressures
 285 as shown in Figure 5 [Right Column]. To perform the pressure cali-
 286 bration, again the objective was initially positioned at $z = 0 \mu\text{m}$
 287 with zero pressure applied to the device. Then the applied pres-
 288 sure was gradually increased at an increment of 100 Pa , which
 289 causes the membrane to deflect downward and get closer to the
 290 objective (note again the microscope is an inverted one). The
 291 applied pressure was controlled by varying the height of an el-
 292 evated water tank which sustains hydrostatic pressure as shown
 293 in the † ESI (Figure S1). While the calibration process appears
 294 complicated, it really took no more than 15 min based on our re-
 295 peated tests. As detailed below in image analysis, by properly
 296 correlating the two sets of particle images, a relation between
 297 the applied pressure and membrane deflection can be achieved,
 298 which will be crucial to inferring pressure measurement based on
 299 particle images in real experiments.

300 2.5 Image Acquisition and Analysis

301 To facilitate device calibration and actual measurement, particle
 302 images were acquired employing the epi-fluorescence technique
 303 relying on an inverted microscope (Olympus IX-71), a scientific
 304 CMOS camera (Phantom VEO 440), and a green LED (Thorlabs
 305 SOLIS-525C M00569931). The camera sensor consist of a matrix
 306 of 2560×1600 pixels of $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$ each, resulting in a phys-
 307 ical size of $25.6 \times 16 \text{ mm}^2$, which, coupled with a $20\times$ objective
 308 and $1.2\times$ camera adaptor, produces a final field of view (FOV)
 309 of $1.06 \times 0.67 \text{ mm}^2$. Unless otherwise noted, for each case a se-
 310 quence of 100 images were acquired at a frame rate of 25 fps.

311 The images were processed using an in-house code in MAT-
 312 LAB R2019a. Briefly, a region of interest (ROI) of nominally
 313 120×120 pixels was selected surrounding the center of the cir-
 314 cular membrane. Extra care was used to make sure at least one

315 fluorescent particle falls within the ROI. While a fluorescent par-
 316 ticle does not need to be centered, the entire particle should be in
 317 view, and the size of the ROI should be adjusted accordingly. To

Fig. 5 A chart illustrating the calibration procedures. The left column contains the position calibration images, whereas the right column contains the pressure calibration images. Each image on the right is to be cross-correlated with all images on the left to identify the best match. The inset shows a sample fitted curve of the cross-correlation coefficients, and the uncertainty corresponding to Z position control is $0.5 \mu\text{m}$.

318 process the calibrate images, the image acquired at each pressure
 319 (e.g., $p = 0.1$ kPa in Figure 5) was cross-correlated with all po-
 320 sition calibration images, and cross-correlation coefficients were
 321 calculated between the specific pressure calibration image and all
 322 position calibration images. Here the goal is to identify the po-
 323 sition calibration image that is the most similar to the specific
 324 pressure calibration image, which is evaluated based on the cross-
 325 correlation coefficient (i.e., a higher cross-correlation coefficient
 326 indicates a better similarity between two images). with all coeffi-
 327 cients calculated, a polynomial curve was fitted using the built-in
 328 “polyfit” function in MATLAB to identify the best match based on
 329 the peak value of the curve (c.f. Figure 5 inset). Since the ob-
 330 jective position is fixed in the pressure calibration, the z location
 331 of the identified position calibration image effectively measures
 332 the amount of deflection corresponding to the specific pressure
 333 calibration image. Using this approach, each pressure calibration
 334 image was matched with a position calibration image, essentially
 335 producing a relationship between the applied pressure and the
 336 membrane deflection (Figure 6).

Fig. 6 Calibrated relationship between applied pressure (kPa) and mem-
 brane deflection (μm) obtained for one pressure sensor used in this study.
 The horizontal error bars represent the uncertainty of Z position control
 (i.e., $0.5 \mu\text{m}$) and the vertical error bars represent the uncertainty of hy-
 drostatic pressure control (i.e., 0.05 kPa).

337 Processing of an actual measurement image taken at an un-
 338 known pressure essentially follows the same way. The target im-
 339 age at the unknown pressure (i.e., to be measured) again was
 340 cross-correlated with all position calibration images, and cross-
 341 correlation coefficients were calculated. The position calibra-
 342 tion image that yields the highest coefficient was then identified,
 343 which effectively measures the amount of deflection correspond-
 344 ing to the target image. The deflection was then substituted into
 345 the pressure-deflection relation obtained in the calibration step
 346 (i.e., Figure 6) to determine the unknown pressure, which com-
 347 pletes the measurement.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Calibrated Pressure-Deflection Relation

Figure 6 shows the pressure–deflection relation obtained for one
 pressure sensor, which was calibrated in the range of 0–2.9 kPa.
 As expected, the applied pressure and membrane deflection show
 good linearity for small deflection in the pressure range of 0–
 1 kPa with a sensitivity of ~ 0.066 kPa/ μm . In the higher pressure
 range, non-linearity starts to arise with an average sensitivity of
 0.13 kPa/ μm . To facilitate pressure calculation and interpolation,
 a second order polynomial was used to fit the data in the entire
 range of 0–2.9 kPa. The root mean square deviation (RMSD) be-
 tween the data points and the fitted curve is less than 0.04 kPa,
 corresponding to $\sim 1.4\%$ of the full-scale value of 2.9 kPa. It is
 worth noting that in the current study, all the membranes and
 sensing chambers were fabricated following exactly the same pro-
 cedures and recipes in a highly repeatable manner, so the cali-
 bration curves are highly similar between different devices and
 different sensors. While it is possible to use the same calibra-
 tion curve for all sensors with acceptable accuracy, we produced
 a separate ad hoc calibration curve for each individual sensing
 chamber and membrane to ensure high accuracy. In addition, to
 rigorously test the pressure sensor for its robustness and potential
 hysteresis, a test calibration was also performed for 4 consecutive
 runs using a separate sensor fabricated in the same way, where
 the applied pressure was varied following a pattern of 0 kPa –
 2.4 kPa – 0 kPa – 2.4 kPa – 0 kPa at a step of 0.2 kPa. As shown in
 † ESI Figure S5, the data from all 4 runs agrees very well, with
 a maximum RMSD of 0.042 kPa (1.75% of the calibrated range)
 between any two runs, suggesting a good repeatability and negli-
 gible hysteresis of the pressure sensor in the calibrated range.

3.2 Application: Pressure Drop in Single-Phase flow

As the first application and validation of the pressure sensor, the
 pressure drop in a microchannel was measured using both air and
 deionized (DI) water as the working fluids at constant flow rates.
 For this measurement, a microchannel of a nominal width, height
 and length of $w = 0.1$ mm, $h = 0.12$ mm, and $l = 18.8$ mm, respec-
 tively, were fabricated as shown in Figure 7. To the upstream and
 downstream of the test channel, two short channels with enlarged
 width ($w = 0.3$ mm) were added to connect the test channel with
 the inlet and outlet. The pressure sensors were then incorpor-
 ated right at the upstream of the inlet and the downstream of the
 outlet to effectively measure the pressure drop across the entire
 test microchannel. It is worth noting that the test microchannel
 was intentionally designed to have a U shape to: (i) reduce the
 footprint of the device, and (ii) place the upstream and down-
 stream sensors close by so that they can be measured simulta-
 neously by fitting both in one FOV of the microscope. For all
 sensors used in this study, the sensing chambers were $200 \mu\text{m}$ in
 diameter, and $\sim 80 \mu\text{m}$ in depth. As illustrated in Figure 7a, the
 flow was controlled by a high-precision syringe pump (Harvard
 Apparatus, PHD 22/2000). Additionally, the pressure different
 between the inlet and outlet was also measured by a commercial
 pressure transducer (Validyne, P55E) as a benchmark reference,
 whose reading was continuously logged using a data acquisition

Fig. 7 Schematic illustrating the pressure drop measurement setup for the single-phase flow (a) and multi-phase flow (b) cases. The test microchannel is 0.1 mm wide, 0.12 mm depth and 18.8 mm long. And the pressure sensors used herein are all 0.2 mm in diameter. The flow rate is controlled by a syringe pump connected to the inlet of the microchannel, whereas the outlet is opened to atmosphere. In the single-phase flow case, the pressure drop across the microchannel is also measured with a differential pressure transducer. In the multi-phase flow case, air was used to displace water at a very low flow rate, and the pressure drop is dominated by the capillary pressure jump across the interface.

402 system (National Instruments, USB-6001).

403 For the air flow experiment, the pressure drop was measured at
 404 flow rates from 0 to 1.2 ml/min with an increment of 0.1 ml/min.
 405 The Reynolds number at the maximum flow rate of 1.2 ml/min
 406 was calculated to be 11.6 based on the hydraulic diameter of the
 407 microchannel, confirming the laminar flow conditions. Following
 408 each increase of flow rate, a minimum waiting time of 1 min
 409 was used to ensure a steady-state flow during image acquisition. The
 410 same MATLAB image analysis algorithm as described in the cal-
 411 ibration procedures was used to calculate the membrane deflection
 412 for each applied flow rate. Once the membrane deflection
 413 was determined, it was substituted into the pressure-deflection
 414 relation (*i.e.*, Figure 6) to determine the pressure exerted at each
 415 of the pressure sensors at upstream and downstream. The differ-
 416 ence between the two pressures yielded the pressure drop across
 417 the microchannel.

418 Figure 8a shows the variation of pressure drop within the mi-
 419 crochannel as a function of flow rate. As expected for laminar
 420 flows, the pressure drop is proportional to the flow rate, result-
 421 ing in a linear relationship. The error bars represent the combined er-
 422 ror propagated from uncertainties in the calibration relation and
 423 uncertainties in the membrane deflection calculation. To validate
 424 the pressure sensor measurement, it is compared with the data
 425 obtained with the commercial pressure transducer. It can be seen
 426 that the two sets of measurement agree very well yielding a RMSD
 427 of 0.028 kPa and a maximum deviation of 0.045 kPa, $\sim 1.5\%$ of
 428 the full scale value. To further validate the experimental measure-
 429 ment, the pressure drop across the microchannel was also numeri-
 430 cally calculated using Star-CCM+ (see † ESI for details), which
 431 was plotted in Figure 8. The numerical results agrees reasonably
 432 well with the experimental measurements with a slight overpre-
 433 diction at the high pressure range. Although this overprediction
 434 is within the measurement uncertainty, we believe this discrepancy
 435 can also be partially attributed to the slight deformation (expan-
 436 sion) of the PDMS microchannel under high pressures⁴⁴, which
 437 was not considered in the simulation. We also note that the pres-
 438 sure drop in a rectangular channel at a given flow rate can also
 439 be theoretically calculated based on the following equation⁴⁵,

$$\Delta p = \frac{4\mu l}{wh^3 \left[\frac{1}{3} - \frac{64h}{\pi^3 w} \tanh\left(\frac{\pi w}{2h}\right) \right]} Q \quad (1)$$

440 where μ is the dynamic viscosity of the working fluid, and Q is the

441 volumetric flow rate through the microchannel. Although data
 442 is not shown here, the theoretical values are also in reasonable
 443 agreement with the experimentally measured values. However,
 444 after careful measurement, it was observed that the microchannel
 445 used herein does not have a perfect rectangular cross-section. In-
 446 stead the cross-sectional is more of a trapezoid shape with curved
 447 edges (see † ESI Figure S2). Therefore, we believe the numerical
 448 simulation result, which was based on the actual 3D geometry of
 449 the microchannel, provides a better representation of the actual
 450 pressure drop in the microchannel as shown in Figure 8a.

451 The same experiment was performed using DI water as the
 452 working fluid at different flow rates. Due to the much higher
 453 dynamic viscosity of water compared with air, the flow rate was
 454 reduced by about two orders of magnitude, so that the pressure
 455 drop falls within the measurement range of the sensors. The
 456 Reynolds number corresponding to the highest flowrate is 1.4,
 457 again confirming laminar flows in the microchannel. Figure 8b
 458 shows the variation of pressure drop within the microchannel
 459 as a function of flow rate using DI water as the working fluid.
 460 Again a good linear relationship between pressure drop and flow
 461 rate is evident, as expected for laminar flows. All three sets of
 462 data show reasonably good agreement, with a RMSD value of
 463 0.036 kPa between the pressure sensor and pressure transducer
 464 measurements. It is also worth noting that, to quantify the poten-
 465 tial hysteresis of the pressure sensor, pressure drop was also mea-
 466 sured by reducing the flow rate from high to low at selected flow
 467 rates (*i.e.*, 1.2 ml/min back to 0 ml/min at a step of 0.2 ml/min in
 468 the air case, and 8 μ l/min back to 0 μ l/min at a step of 2 μ l/min
 469 in the water case). The maximum deviations between the up and
 470 down runs are 0.04 kPa and 0.03 kPa for the air and water cases,
 471 respectively, which both fall within the measurement uncertainty,
 472 confirming very little, if any, hysteresis of the pressure sensor.

3.3 Application: Capillary Pressure in Multi-Phase Flow

473 The capillary pressure measurement in an air-water multi-phase
 474 flow was conducted using a similar setup as used for the single-
 475 phase flow. To initiate the experiments, the microchannel was
 476 first presaturated with DI water using the syringe pump at a flow
 477 rate of 5 μ l/min. Extra care was taken during this step to prevent
 478 any air bubbles from getting into the microchannel. Then the sy-
 479 ringe pump was paused for a minimum of 5 min to allow the flow
 480

Fig. 8 Pressure drop at various flow rates obtained using our sensor (red symbols), the commercial pressure transducer (blue symbols) and numerical simulation (green lines) for the single-phase flows of air (a) and water (b). The error bars associated with the PDMS sensor data indicated the overall propagated uncertainties (0.07 kPa, $\sim 2.4\%$ of the full scale value) from the calibrate relation and membrane deflection measurement. The transducer data error bars are based on the manufacturer-specified accuracy. And the dashed lines are the upper and lower bounds of the numerical values ($\pm 8\%$), again based on propagated errors mainly from channel dimension measurements.

Fig. 9 Photos of water droplets on a PDMS surface under (a) static condition and (b) receding condition. To create the receding contact line, the water was instantaneously withdrawn from the droplet using a pipette. Both images were processed in ImageJ, and the static and receding contact angles turned out to be 110° and 57° , respectively.

481 to subside. Next air was slowly injected into the microchannel at
 482 the same flow rate of $5 \mu\text{l}/\text{min}$. As the air enters the microchan-
 483 nel, an air-water interface is created, which generates a pressure
 484 jump (capillary pressure) across the interface due to surface ten-
 485 sion and interfacial curvature. It is worth noting that PDMS is
 486 slightly hydrophobic under static conditions. In fact, our mea-
 487 surement shows that the static contact angle of water on PDMS
 488 surface is 110° (Figure 9a). However, in this case when water is
 489 being displaced out of the microchannel, what is relevant is the
 490 receding contact angle. Our measurement indicated a receding
 491 contact angle of 57° for a droplet water shrinking on PDMS
 492 surface (Figure 9b). The entire process of air displacing water
 493 was recorded and again processed in MATLAB as discussed earlier.

494 Figure 10 shows the raw particle images for both upstream and
 495 downstream sensors, right before and after the air-water inter-
 496 face passes the downstream sensor. When the air-water inter-

497 face is between the two pressure sensors (Figure 10a), the mem-
 498 brane in the upstream sensor undergoes a large deflection as evi-
 499 dent from the horizontally elongated particle images, suggest-
 500 ing a high pressure is exerted on the upstream pressure sensor.
 501 The downstream sensor on the other hand shows very little mem-
 502 brane deflection as evident from the vertically elongated particle
 503 images. Due to the low dynamic viscosity of air and the extremely
 504 low flow rate, the contribution of viscous pressure drop of air is
 505 largely negligible. Therefore, the pressure difference between the
 506 upstream and downstream sensors is essentially due the capil-
 507 lary pressure generated across the interface. However, when the
 508 air-water interface passes the downstream sensor (Figure 10b),
 509 the upstream sensor immediately resume to its initial condition,
 510 with little pressure difference detected between the upstream and
 511 downstream sensors, as expected.

512 Based on the particle images, the capillary pressure across
 513 the air-water interface in the microchannel was measured to be
 514 1.54 kPa . A theoretical value of the capillary pressure was calcu-
 515 lated using the Young-Laplace equation based on the microchan-
 516 nel dimensions, the water-air surface tension and the receding
 517 contact angle¹⁶,

$$p^c = 2\sigma\left(\frac{1}{w} + \frac{1}{d}\right)\cos\theta \quad (2)$$

518 where p^c is the capillary pressure, σ is the surface tension of wa-
 519 ter ($0.072 \text{ N}/\text{m}$), w and d are the width (0.096 mm) and depth
 520 (0.12 mm) of the microchannel, respectively, and θ (57°) is the
 521 receding contact angle of the water phase. Note due to the trape-
 522 zoidal shape of the cross section, w here was taken at the narrow-
 523 est point, which is believed to dominate the capillary pressure¹⁶.

Fig. 10 Particle image shapes of the upstream and downstream sensors before (a) and after (b) the air-water interface passes the downstream sensor. When capillary pressure jump exists between the two sensors (a), the upstream sensor is subject to high pressure; when the interface exits the test channel (b), both sensors are subject to low pressure.

Based on Equation 2 and the physical values, the theoretical capillary pressure was calculated to be 1.47 kPa, which deviates from the measured value by 0.07 kPa (4.5%), within the measurement uncertainty of 0.07 kPa of the pressure sensor. This result represents a big improvement compared with previous capillary pressure measurement based on interfacial curvature¹⁶.

The last thing to note is that properties of PDMS are known to change over time (e.g., bulk materials get stiffer over time)⁴⁶. To ensure that our results are not significantly impacted by this effect, all the experiments were performed within 10 hours of the calibration. Additionally, a stability test was carried out to determine the change of the calibration curve of the same sensor over 24 hours. The membrane indeed got slightly more rigid over time, leading to a higher pressure in the second test for the same amount of membrane deflection. Although results are not shown, the RMSD between the two curves is found to be 0.035 kPa, which is $\sim 1.2\%$ of the full scale. Nevertheless, this relatively small shift of material properties further justifies our measurement quality.

4 Conclusions

A membrane-based microfluidic pressure sensor has been successfully designed and fabricated using simple soft lithography. By embedding 1 μm fluorescent particles into the thin membrane, and using Astigmatic Particle Tracking scheme, the membrane deflection is detected based on the shape of the particles. The simple optical readout method and image processing algorithm have led to fast and precise pressure measurements under single and multi-phase flow conditions in the microchannel. The current sensor has a measurement range of 0–2.9 kPa with an accuracy of 70 Pa. The sensor has been successfully applied to measure the pressure drop within a microchannel for single-phase flow of air

and DI water. Good agreement has been achieved between the pressure sensor, a commercial pressure transducer and numerical simulation results. Additionally, to the best of our knowledge, the sensor has for the first time successfully measured the capillary pressure across the air-water interface with a 7% deviation from the theoretical value. The capability demonstrated by the pressure sensor is promising and this work opens the door to a renewed understanding of pore-scale physics of multi-phase flow in porous media.

Although the current study only demonstrated the use of two pressure sensors in a microchannel, as the next step a 2D array of pressure taps will be fabricated to enable a true 2D pressure field mapping, which can be achieved by a simple change of the photomask design. Moreover, although not explored in the current study, the sensitivity and measurement range of the pressure sensor can be finely tuned by adjusting parameters such as the pressure sensor size, PDMS membrane thickness, and even the Young's modulus of the PDMS material. A parametric study of the system will be carried out in a future study to gain a better understanding of the device performance, and help to accommodate more challenging measurements, such as 2D pressure mapping of multi-phase flow in porous media. Finally, surface wettability is a well-known issue of the PDMS material. Although the naturally hydrophobic PDMS surfaces can be made hydrophilic by exposing them to an air or oxygen plasma, such modification is known to be unstable⁴⁷. Additionally, PDMS itself is incompatible with many solvents and oils, all of which may limit its application in many multi-phase flow scenarios⁴⁸. To partially alleviate this issue, we will explore different elastic materials and/or different types of coatings to further expand its compatibility.

Author Contributions

Nishagar Raventhiran: Methodology, Data acquisition, Data curation, Writing - Original draft preparation. Razin Sazzad Molla: Methodology, Data acquisition. Kshithij Nandishwara: Software, Data curation, Validation. Erick Johnson: Supervision, Software, Writing- Reviewing and Editing. Yaofa Li: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data acquisition, Data curation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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